

The Implementation Of Policy On Expansion Development Of Employment Opportunities For Productive Workforce In Tidore City

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Abstract: The purpose of this research is to determine the expansion development and government policy to develop employment chance for the productive workforce in Tidore City. This research used observation, interview and documentation to collect the primary and secondary data, and using the qualitative method to analyse the data. The data obtained from the Department of labour and transmigration in Tidore City. The results showed that the development of employment opportunities had been done through the program of expanding employment opportunities and increasing the workforce competence. The government of Tidore City has also exploited the expansion of employment for productive-age workers, and through the Office of Manpower and Transmigration, the government of Tidore City has facilitated productive workforce through training and apprenticeship for skilled workers in developing skills and competencies. The government has been assisting the workers with internship and training to improve their competence and expertise. Therefore, the local government to provide the budget to expand and develop the employment as well as to strengthen the cooperation with the private employer and regional owned enterprise to extend the job, to manage, and to decrease the capacity of workers consistently.

Index Terms: Productive workforce, job opportunities, employment development, Tidore Island.

1 INTRODUCTION

The development and expansion of employment opportunities is still a problem that has not been solved completely. The central government and local government fully realise this as a symptom of increasing population and lack of space for job seekers to get a decent job and following the competence, it has. Besides, there is also a need for more qualified employees in line with increasing educational qualifications and workforce capacity. This problematic reading as a potential problem in the future can occur if no solutions are found. The limited amount of labour absorption, of course also affect the social and economic dimensions of a region. Therefore, it is important to immediately consider the integrated settlement measures by involving all interested stakeholders to formulate appropriate policy models to anticipate them. Government policy in the field of the workforce has been confirmed in Law Number 13 (2003) on Manpower. Referring to Article 27 paragraph (2) of the 1945 Indonesia Constitution which mandates that "Every citizen shall have the right to work and a decent living for humanity". To support the policy in the field of the workforce has been issued Government Regulation No. 33 (2013) About Expansion of Employment Opportunities. Thus, the regional government should conduct the structuring, development and expansion of employment opportunities for the people in its area. As with other regions, the people of Tidore City also need the presence of local government policies that are more in favour of solving development problems and expanding employment opportunities.

Based on Tidore City population data, the total population of this city has reached 98,206 by the end of 2017. Indeed, every year is sure to increase the number of job seekers [1]. The number of job seekers in Tidore City is predicted to be 30% of the population, while the number of job seekers is predicted to be 90% of the total number of job seekers. Tidore City is experiencing limited employment. Moreover, the community is more dependent on the work provided by the government, especially in the field of infrastructure development. Another thing is also seen in the high interest of undergraduate to take government employees. The government should pay attention to this to respond more quickly by stimulating the growth of other economic sectors, such as the development of agriculture, fisheries and infrastructure to create employment opportunities for the workforce every year. Factors causing the lack of job opportunities generated by internal and external factors. Internal factors are related to the low level of education, poverty, capital constraints, lack of skills, and the lack of interest in productive working groups to open independent employment, while external factors are related to government policies in the field of labour [2]. Based on the above description, the issue of policy development and the expansion of labour in Tidore City is significant to be studied. It is hoped that the results of this research can be the necessary information and references of policy making for the regional government.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Implementation of Policy

Implementation is an action or application of a well-crafted and detailed plan. Implementation is usually done after the planning is considered perfect. The implementation is derived from activities, operations, actions or the existence of a system mechanism, the application is not just an activity, but a planned event and to achieve the purpose of the activity [3, 4]. The implementation is an extension of activities that mutually adjust the process of interaction between the objectives and actions to achieve them and require a capable network of implementers, bureaucracy [5]. The implementation leads to the mechanism of a system. Based on the opinion it can be concluded that execution is a planned activity, not just an

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activity and done seriously based on the reference to certain norms to achieve the purpose of the event. Therefore, the implementation does not stand alone but is influenced by the next object of the curriculum. Implementation of the curriculum is the process of implementing new ideas, programs or activities in the hope that others can receive and make changes to learning and obtain the expected results [3]. Many variables or factors will determine the success of the implementation, and each of these variables is related to each other. To enrich our understanding of the various variables involved in the application. Policy implementation is influenced by four variables, such as; (1) communication, (2) resources, (3) disposition, and (4) bureaucratic structure. The four variables are also interconnected with each other [6]. The effectiveness of policy implementation requires that the implementer know what to do. What are the policy objectives and targets should be transmitted to the target group so that it will reduce the implementation distortion? If the goals and objectives of the policy are unclear or even unknown to the target group, there is a possibility of resistance from the target group. Although the contents of the administration have been communicated and consistent, if the implementer lacks the resources to implement, the implementation will not run effectively. These resources can manifest human resources, namely the competence of the implementer and financial resources. Resources are essential factors for the implementation of the policy to be effective. Without resources, the system remains on paper only. Disposition is the character and characteristics of the implementer. If the implementer has a proper distribution, then he or she will run the policy as well as what the policymaker wants. When implementer has different attitudes or perspectives with politicians, the policy implementation process is also ineffective. Various development experiences in third world countries show that the level of commitment and honesty of the apparatus is low. Multiple cases of corruption that emerge in third world countries, such as Indonesia is a concrete example of the low commitment and honesty of the apparatus in implementing development programs. The organisational structure in charge of implementing the policy has a significant influence on the implementation of the system. One of the most important structural aspects of any organisation is the existence of standard operating procedures (SOPs). SOPs serve as guidelines for every implementer in action. An overly long organisational structure will tend to undermine surveillance and lead to red-tape, complicated and complex bureaucratic procedures, which in turn leads to inflexible corporate activity.

Concepts and Theories of Manpower

The process of regional development requires the active participation of the community as the primary driver of growth. On the other hand, the government plays an active role in encouraging the policy-making process towards the development process through the formulation, regulation, implementation, and monitoring of development and the involvement of the community in development. The method of development is not only marked by changes in the structure of demand and supply of goods and services, but the process of economic growth is also characterised by changes in population structure and employment [7]. Changes in population structure necessarily imply the limited available employment opportunities. Therefore, it is necessary to extend labour absorption efforts to compensate for the growth rate of

young people who enter the labour market. An imbalance between the growth of the labour force and job creation will lead to high unemployment. Higher unemployment rates will result in the wasting of resources and potential of the existing workforce, increasing public burdens, the primary source of poverty and promoting social unrest, and long-term economic development [8]. The manpower is everyone who is willing to work, where the workforce includes all those who work both for themselves or for family members who do not receive compensation in the form of wages or all persons who are actually willing and able to work, in the real sense of their being willing and able to work, in the mind that they are unemployed forced by lack of job opportunities [9]. The need for labour is based on the idea that labour in society is one of the potential factors in overall economic development. The available employment opportunities and the quality of work used will determine the process of economic growth with the understanding that the labour force takes resources to run the production process as well as the goods and services market. In this case, the need for labour depends on the available employment opportunities in an economy [10]. Similarly, the meaning of the workforce that is everyone who is willing and able to work, including those who are unemployed even though willing and able to work and those who are unemployed forced due to no job opportunities. Further, the aged workforce is a productive workforce and must have unique skills to enter the labour market [11]. The labour can be divided into two groups, which is the labour force and not the labour force. The labour force is a resident of the working age group who is working or looking for a job, have permanent employment but are temporarily unemployed and have no job at all, but remain active in finding employment. While work has a meaning to do various activities to produce goods and services with the aim of earning income at a particular time [12]. The labour force is part of the workforce involved or is trying to engage in productive activities. The labour force can be subdivided into two sections, namely workers and unemployed. The workforce is a part of the population capable and willing to do the work. The meaning of being able is to be able to be physically and physically, mentally and juridically competent, and not to lose the freedom to choose and do the work and to be willing to actively or passively perform and seek employment [9]. The number of the labour force has increased every year. Such conditions are not directly proportional to the availability of space for the labour force to find decent employment. The point of this problem stems from the gap between the growth of the labour force on the one hand and the ability of different sectors of the economy to absorb labour on the other. The labour demand relates to the amount of labour required by a particular company or agency. Further, identifies that demand for demand determination of labour, which is as follows [13]; salary rate, technology, productivity, labour quality, and capital facilities. Meanwhile, employment opportunities generally can be defined as circumstances that reflect how much of the total workforce can be absorbed or actively participated in economic activities. Every individual who has enough age in the workforce would want to get a job following the skills it has. Working becomes an essential part so that everyone can independently be able to meet the needs of everyday life, so get a decent job to improve its economic level.

Local Government Policy

Tidore City is a part of North Maluku Province, where domestic government policies are profoundly affected by domestic politics. Therefore, sometimes local government policies must follow local political conditions of the region so that the systems taken are the result of agreement according to local politics [17-19], especially labour policy. Employment issues are always a hot issue in governance. Government policy can have an impact directly or indirectly in the joints of people's lives. Considering that labour issues will potentially be a problem in the future if it is not handled early, the government is obliged to make breakthroughs through policies that favour the creation of employment opportunities for the community. The fundamental problem in formulating policy is related to the steps of the solution. Expressing policy issues means appropriately translating policy issues while formulating policies relating to the design of Government actions to address these public issues. The answer to each policy problems varies widely as a result of multiple viewpoints because of the problem. An early attempt to gather various possible steps for policy-solving was made in the identification of alternatives. In this process, the Government seeks to accumulate the multiple possibilities available as policy options. In collecting the available options, the government does not have to collect as many options as the government has its limitations. Once the alternative is identified, then the choice is then formulated [14]. Furthermore, one way to expand employment is through the development of industry, especially labour-intensive sectors. Growth can be realised through private and government investment. The development of the sector will lead to increased production capacity to create employment opportunities. Workforce capable of being absorbed from employment depends on wages, capital, productivity and technology [15]. Further, to realise the purpose of optimising the use of labour and employment, there must be a functional linkage between employment policies and labour policies. Employment opportunities should guide sectoral policies regarding the direction to be addressed. Here the objective of the expansion of employment opportunities outlined for each sector should be a general objective in addition to the specific sector objectives. Meanwhile, labour policies are sector-specific responsibilities for agencies handling labour. Labour policies should serve sectoral and regional development in meeting the needs of eligible workers and maintain a healthy, peaceful and harmonious working environment [16].

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The type of this research is qualitative research with descriptive methods that is research which try to reveal intact, systematic, factual and accurate about data and fact happened in the field. From here, the authors will get the whole, process and policy of Local Government which has been and has been implemented to overcome the problem of development and expansion of employment opportunities for productive working age. This research was conducted at the Office of Manpower and Transmigration of Tidore City. The location of this study was selected from several substantial reasons, i.e. the Department of Manpower and Transmigration is a policymaker dealing with matters of employment in Tidore City. Another reason, the Office of Manpower and Transmigration is given the authority to develop strategic plans and policy scenarios in employment matters both in providing,

opportunities and the development of productive workers. Data collection by conducting direct observation to research location in the object intending to obtain a real picture of activities on data performance then as analysis matter of problems studied. Therefore, view used as supporting data. The interview is a question and answer process to get the data used as the basis of argument in research. Interview techniques are used as data collection techniques if conducts preliminary studies to address issues to be investigated. Furthermore, the data were analysis descriptively qualitative using the Interactive model as follows [20]; 1) data reduction; 2) presentation of data and 3) conclusions. The validity of data required inspection techniques. The implementation of inspection techniques is based on four criteria [21]; 1) credibility; 2) transferability; 3) dependability; and 4) confirmability.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Implementation of Labor Expansion Policy

Opening job opportunities to the community are the responsibility of the government for the creation of a just and prosperous society as mandated by the Indonesian Constitution to create community welfare. Both central and local governments are responsible for creating the expansion of employment opportunities to communities by working with private parties and government-owned enterprises as mandated by Law 13 (2003) on employment. Labor Law No. 13 (2003) in articles 29, paragraph 1 through paragraph 4, indicates to both central and regional governments to promote the expansion of employment opportunities and financial institutions, both banking and non-banking, and the business world needs to assist and provide convenience for every activity communities that can create or develop an expansion of employment opportunities. Article 40 implies that the development of employment opportunities outside of employment is done through the creation of productive and sustainable activities by utilising the potential of natural resources, human resources and appropriate technology. The production of expansion of employment opportunities is done by the pattern of formation and self-employment, the implementation of labour-intensive systems, the application of appropriate technology, and the utilisation of voluntary labour or other models that can encourage the creation of expansion of employment opportunities. Article 41 requires the Government to establish employment policies and the development of employment opportunities. Besides, governments and communities do not have the authority to oversee the implementation of employment expansion policies jointly. Following the legislation that requires the government to extend the employment expansion, the Office of Manpower and Transmigration, Tidore Government follows up on several policies: training, apprenticeship, assistance and employment expansion. Development of employment opportunities is done through labour-intensive activities, self-employment, appropriate technology, and labour-intensive. All programs and activities aim to provide employment opportunities for prospective job seekers as well as opportunities to create their employment. Based on data recording of Manpower and Transmigration Office of Tidore City, several activities have been conducted which are part of the policy of expansion of employment opportunities within five years, i.e. from 2014 to 2017. The data can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Labor Expansion Policy

Types of Policy	Years
Infrastructure Works	2014 until now
Productive Workforce	2014 until now
Activity Self-employment	2014 until now
Appropriate technology	2014 until now
Special labour	2014 until now

Based on interviews with respondents consisting of policymakers and the community. There is some information about the implementation of the employment expansion policy. According to respondents who are also heads of labour in the Office of Manpower and Transmigration of Tidore City, several systems are oriented to the expansion of employment opportunities with the primary target of decreasing unemployment rate as in Table 1. The implementation of employment opportunities expansion policy by the Office of Manpower and Transmigration has provided significant benefits to the community. Based on the results of interviews with respondents, i.e. the community involved in the program and activities of the labour and transmigration service, feel the benefits. They revealed that with labour-intensive work programs, for example, communities could be involved in the development process and get income to meet their needs. Based on the data obtained of interviews with the community explains, 75% of respondents admitted grateful and grateful to the Office of Manpower and Transmigration Tidore City which has given them the opportunity to follow the activities and human resources development programs labor, 25% of respondents said they did not know because they were never involved in the events. People who have felt the positive impact of the policy on employment expansion, the public is well aware that this government policy is beneficial in providing employment opportunities for communities to address the problem of unemployment. Labour intensive activities, for example, can absorb as many as 88 workers per package of events, where each year held 20 packets of labour-intensive activities. So there are as many as 1320 churches who are working to complete the event. Coupled with other activities such as appropriate technology and limited workload. All of this is a good policy taken by the Manpower and Transmigration Office to reduce unemployment rates and increase the extension of employment opportunities for job seekers.

Model of Job Opportunity Development in Tidore City

The development of employment opportunities in Tidore City is done through several approaches, namely the development of human resources for job seekers, cooperation in job opening and improvement of job seeker competence. These three approaches are described in every development policy of work maturity by the Office of Manpower and Transmigration. The systems on the job development model can be seen in the strategic plan (*RENSTRA*) and work plan (*RENJA*) of Manpower and Transmigration Office of Tidore City. The *RENSTRA* contains strategic policies regarding employee development since 2015 has been formulated a strategic plan for five years following the general theory of Tidore City administration included in *RPJMD*. Work programs that are part of the strategic policy are 1) skill development through training to prospective workers; 2) cooperation with government and private sector for job opening; increased

competence through apprenticeship. These policies are oriented towards human resource development of job seekers or prospective workers to be absorbed by the work field and can open their skills and competence it has. Increased capacity of a worker or skill is an effort to develop skills and work experience. The development process can be done through some approach either self-study (autodidact) and trained by experts. Training activities are one unique approach, where prospective workers are specially trained by experts who have specific skills in a particular field. For example, furniture training, workshop training, graphic design training, clothes design training and others. Based on the results of the interviews with the policymakers at the Manpower and Immigration Office and with the job seekers who have attended the training, express their appreciation and full support for the implementation of the training activities. According to them, this training is beneficial for improving the quality of prospective job seekers, can even give birth to entrepreneurs or who create new jobs with skills or competencies it has. The employment opportunities model for job seekers in Tidore City has been conducted in partnership with government and private institutions. Based on the data that there is a policy of cooperation between the State Electricity Company (*PLN*) and Training Center (*BLK*) in the implementation of training to the community both in the field of electricity, carpentry, agriculture, and others. The cooperation aims to involve government agencies and the private sector that can help train prospective workers in Tidore City to have the skills and competence in specific fields. The Government of Tidore City through the Office of Manpower and Transmigration has implemented programs and internship activities for the last five years. This internship aims to send ambassadors of prospective workers from Tidore City to areas that have advanced home industry. It is hoped that with this training, the apprentices can take their knowledge and then after the apprenticeship then return to Tidore City, the experience and skills can be developed by forming their home industry or inviting the same friends to participate in training to the workgroup to open the own business.

Productive Workforce in Tidore City

Based on data from Manpower and Transmigration Office shows that the percentage of the productive workforce is 30% of the total population of 98,206, the population of 49,551 male and 48,965 female (*BPS, 2017*). This provides information to the government as the policymaker that this productive workforce with such a large number requires the provision of large jobs as well. If employment is available, and the productive workforce is channelled, it will have an impact on the economic growth rate in Tidore City. Labour supply is the number of people willing to work at a certain salary level. Usually, the amount of labour supply is known from the workforce population whose main activity a week ago is working or looking for a job. Labour supply is the number of people who are ready to work, called the workforce that can be seen regarding quality and quantity. Labour supply is the sum of the workforce consisting of people who work and find work. While the working population is referred to as labour demand. The difference between inventories minus the need is called unemployment (job seekers) [22]. Local governments as policymakers must provide employment opportunities to facilitate this productive workforce to work, which will lead to a decrease in unemployment rates in Tidore City. Based on data

obtained from the *BPS* survey report in 2017 showed that the unemployment rate in Tidore City amounted to 3.59% of the total workforce, as seen in Table 2.

Table 2. The percentage of the population aged over 15 years old

Tabel 3.2.1		Persentase Penduduk Berumur 15 Tahun ke Atas menurut Jenis Kegiatan Utama di Kota Tidore Kepulauan, 2015-2016	
Table		Percentage of Population 15 Years of Age Above by Main Activity in Tidore Kepulauan City, 2015-2016	
Jenis Kegiatan Utama Main Activity		2015	2016
(1)	(2)	(3)	
I. Angkatan Kerja/Economically Active			
1. Bekerja/Working	94.16	...	
2. Penganggur/Unemployment	3.59	...	
II. Bukan Angkatan Kerja (Sekolah Mengurus Rumah Tangga dan Lainnya)/Not Economically Active (Attending School Housekeeping and Others)			
	33.25	...	
Jumlah/Total	100	...	
Tingkat Partisipasi Angkatan Kerja (TPAK) Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPRs)	66.75	...	
Tingkat Pengangguran Terbuka (TPT) Open Unemployment Rate (OURs)	3.69	...	
Sumber : BPS Kota Tidore Kepulauan Hasil Survei Angkatan Kerja Nasional Agustus 2016 Source : BPS-Statistics of Tidore Kepulauan City Result of National Labour Force Survey August 2016			

Based on Table 2, most of the unemployed is a productive workforce. Therefore, the local government has taken a policy to overcome the problem of unemployment, especially the unemployment of productive workers through training and apprenticeship policy. Training and apprenticeship are prioritised for the productive workforce from 20 - 30 years old. The training and apprenticeship are aimed at improving skills and developing skill capacity and employment practices to produce productive, skilled workers, primarily directed to become entrepreneurs or young entrepreneurs who in turn become job creators, not job seekers. Workforce and Transmigration offices of Tidore City in 2017 has conducted training on workshops, carpentry, agriculture, graphic design, the design of clothing and handicrafts. The output of this training has generated entrepreneurship of 150 industrial home groups and 800 prospective workers as well as 80 independent businesses spread across all districts in Tidore City. The population status in the employment analysis is divided into two groups: the working age population and the non-working age population. In Indonesia, the working age population is defined as a population aged 15 and above. The working age population in Tidore City in 2017 reached 69,004 people or 69.46 per cent of the total population of 98,206 people. When viewed by gender, the working age population in Tidore City (2017) consists of 49,551 male population and 48,965 female population. Workforce populations are classified into two groups: the labour force and not the labour force. With these groupings, we can see how far people have the opportunity to engage in economic activity. By 2017, the workforce in Tidore City reached 60.92 per cent (42,039 people) of the total working age population, while the remaining 39.08 per cent or 27,005 people excluded the workforce, as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The percentage of the workforce population by main activity in Tidore City, 2017

Available job opportunities resulting from economic activity (production) in this case include already filled employment and all vacant jobs. Considering the data on actual labour needs is difficult to obtain, practical uses are used where the number of labour needs is approached through the number of filled employment as reflected by the employed population. The working population is referred to as demand for labour.

Implementation of Expanded Employment Opportunity Policy for Productive Workforce in Tidore City

Productive workforce training

Productive workforce training is directed to potential work areas in Tidore City. The training was conducted in the machine workshop and bamboo handicraft. These two areas were chosen because based on the survey results conducted, in these two areas there are significant economic opportunities because the level of community needs for workshop services and bamboo handicraft services is very high. All participants who participated in the training are taught to understand the techniques of making bamboo crafts following the desired field. The trainees also received assistance in the form of workshop equipment and equipment for making bamboo handicrafts such as chairs and others. This assistance is given to developing the talents and skills they have. The output obtained from training activities for this productive age has spawned several creative business groups in Tidore City, which is a productive workforce aged between 20-24 years old. Based on data owned by the Office of Manpower and Transmigration, within the last five years, 30 business units have been formed by creative groups of training-resulted outcomes by the Office of Manpower and Transmigration of Tidore City. The business unit is divided into four types of business namely workshop, carpentry, bamboo handicraft and graphic design. Workforce planning can be done through the supply side and the needs side. On the supply side, more about the number and quality of labour, employment planning tends to address issues related to prospective workers or those who will be newcomers to the workforce. Workforce planning from the demand side is derived demand where new labouring needs will exist if there is demand for goods and services produced by the community.

Productive Workforce Apprenticeship

The process of developing the productive workforce in Tidore City is done through the apprenticeship program at the modern home and craft centre. During the last five years have been sent ambassadors of the productive workforce as many as 50 people in several areas like Bandung, Jepara, Semarang, and Yogyakarta. Based on interviews results of the guidance head section, training and placement of labor obtained information that every year programmed internship for prospective employers of productive age. During the last five years, internships have been held in Bandung, internships in the manufactured home, screen printing and product packaging design; Yogyakarta internship about bamboo handicraft; Jepara apprenticed about the process of making skill in the field of furniture; Semarang apprentice about making Viber/shipyard. The apprenticeship policy with the areas whose services are badly needed by the people in Tidore City has spawned several creative endeavours by creative candidates after apprenticeship. The output of the apprenticeship program has resulted in a creative business venture that is a new business field and allows for employment in Tidore City including the opening of shipyard business in *Rum* Village, opening of business in *Goto* Village, the opening of beauty salon in *Soffi* Village, the opening of bamboo handicraft business in *Tuguwaji* Village. The opening of new businesses as a result of the development of creative enterprises by the productive age workers after apprenticeship shows that the policies taken by the government have been able to reduce unemployment, create new jobs and be able to open employment opportunities for other communities through established businesses. The internship program, programmed over the last five years has sent 50, and 50 of the interns have formed 50 new business units requiring an average of 10 workers. Therefore, the total workforce that can be absorbed from the policy as much as 500 workers. This process will grow in line with the development of the business venture that was built.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In general, the regional government of Tidore City has strived in supporting the implementation of the policy of expansion of employment opportunities for the workforce covering the programs and activities of the projected every year that is *Padat Karya* infrastructure that absorbs 88 workers, productive workforce totaling 66 workers, 400 self-employment, appropriate technology as many as 400 manpower and particular workforce of 400 workers. The employment development model in Tidore City is implemented through various approaches, namely the development of human resources for job seekers, cooperation with the government and private parties in the opening of employment and enhancement of competence through apprenticeship. The productive age unemployment rate has a more significant percentage that is 30% of the total population of Tidore City of 98,206 peoples.

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